

The Role of Sectors in the Socio-Demographic Process of Nukus

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ABSTRACT: It is natural that all modern small towns move to the level of megacities. The city of Nukus is trying to accept this status on the basis of its socio-demographic process, but it is natural that the bigger the city, the more problems. The main challenge for the rise of Nukus to the level of a megalopolis is to determine the evolutionary demographic growth of the population, to study the climatic conditions, to identify and improve the social infrastructure of the population. The climate of the urban nature, the social infrastructure of the population, the areas and shortcomings of each sector were studied. The result of the active movement of sectors to implement the state program in all areas of the city will serve to prepare for the level of the megalopolis.

KEYWORDS: megalopolis, Aral Sea region, Makan citizens' assembly, sector area, demographic factors, agglomeration.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the world civilization, the socio-demographic development of each city is closely linked with the local climate, the economy is strengthened and beautiful architectural objects are created. As a result, the urbanization of the city is formed and a megalopolis is formed. It is more difficult for cities along the South Aral Sea to rise to the level of megacities. This is due to the fact that at the beginning of the XXI century, due to salt storms on the bottom of the Aral Sea, 700 million tons of salty sand arised every year.[1]

According to the world standard, cities with 1 mln population are included in the megalopolis [2]. If there is only one Tashkent city in Uzbekistan, it will take 5 years for Samarkand and at least 10 years for Nukus to reach the level of a megalopolis. 34.1 million people live in our country, while 39 million live in Tokyo, the capital of Japan. [3]. 14 million population resides in central Tokyo. the population has doubled due to agglomeration.

In Tokyo, for example, there are more than 6,000 people per square kilometer, while in Nukus there are 1,612. [4] Like Tokyo, Nukus has the potential to increase the area and population of the surrounding Kegeyli, Khojeyli, Amudarya, Nukus districts in the form of an agglomeration, but this area does not meet the standard of urban demand. In order to accept the city as a megalopolis, first of all it is necessary to happen a threefold increase in the number of population, improve the social living conditions of the population in the area of threefold increase and prepare from now to adapt the conditions of the neighboring district to the city level. The master plan of Nukus was prepared under the direction of architect S.Ovsyannikov [5]. The reasons for being in the city of Nukus in the Aral Sea region at the level of a megalopolis in the coming years are as follows:

On January 18, 2017, the President signed a resolution "On the State Program of Development of the Aral Sea Region for 2017-2021." It includes the development of water supply systems and increase the level of access to clean drinking water, improvement of sewerage, sanitation and household waste management systems; to continue the implementation of measures aimed at improving the living conditions of the population living in the region; It is planned to develop transport, engineering and communication infrastructure, improve the irrigation network and introduce modern energy-saving technologies in the region's settlements.

On October 24-25, 2019 in Nukus and Muynak under the auspices of the United Nations was held the International Conference "The Aral Sea - a zone of environmental innovation and technology"; [6]. 6.1 mln euros and 3.2mln. dollars were allocated to finance projects in the Aral Sea region.

II. MAIN PART

Currently, the population of Nukus is 18% of Karakalpakstan. Karakalpakstan has an average population of 11 people per square kilometer, Nukus has a population of 1,612, it proves that 60% of Karakalpakstan, the Kyzylkum and Ustyurt plateaus are uninhabitable, and Nukus is densely populated. [7] The reason for the increase in population in Nukus was the ecological process after the depletion of the Aral Sea, due to the population of the districts located around the sea such as Karauzak, Chimbai, Taxtakupir, Kungrad, Muynak decreased in growth and move to Nukus, migration has overflowed since 1960 or for 60 years.

Socio-demographic characteristics of the population are one of the necessary factors determining the structure of the city and the nature of the functional organization. The main aspects of demography: the size of the population in production, the mental structure, the image of family life, economic processes, etc. The reason for the high growth of the socio-demographic

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development of the population of Nukus is mainly the large number of production jobs in conjunction with administrative workplaces and the mass allocation of 600m² of land for housing construction.

Due to the unfavorable environmental situation in the ecological zones of the northern Aral Sea region of Karakalpakstan, 30% of population migration is to other regions of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Russia, other republics and 10% to the city of Nukus. This has dramatically changed the pace of migration in Karakalpakstan and Nukus.

This process began during the Soviet era, mainly in 1987, and led to a sharp increase in the population of Nukus. They used their oppression and illegally settled in the shady areas of the city. Over time, it has also had an impact on the construction and development on the outskirts of the city. As a result of this process, the distance between education, medical institutions, utilities, engineering facilities and farms has exceeded the norm, and the balance of urban planning has been disturbed. For example, if the distance between a family living in Jideli-baysun town and a school is, according to the norm, max 1km, here it is 3km. Gas and sewage pipes for 1,000 households have tripled in population, and each household has a problem for gas supply in winter and water supply in summer.

As a result, it does not meet the standards of architectural and social infrastructure in the suburbs Kos kol-1, Kos kol-2, Samanbay, Jideli Baysun and several other towns.

Following the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a meeting of citizens were formed and separated for a comprehensive study of the city. by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 7, 2013 No 274. Spatial civic gatherings play an important role in determining and perfecting the demographic and social development of the city of Nukus. The task of the local citizens' assembly is to study the social infrastructure of the population in its territory, or to identify the unemployed, to maintain peace and harmony in each family, to inform the relevant staff in case of illegal construction, 4 states have been allocated. 1st Place Citizens' Chairman; 2- secretary; 3- guard; 4 Women's Fund Officer.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 8, 2017 No. PP-3182, local assemblies of the city of Nukus were attached to 4 sectors (Figure 1). As a result, it is easier to determine the living conditions of all citizens in the urban area, the socio-infrastructure level of urban citizens, low-income farms. Clarification of demographic data plays an important role in the economic development of the city.

According to the state program, all cities of the Republic of Uzbekistan are divided into 4 sectors, just as Nukus is divided into 4 sectors. At the same time, the goal is to increase the number of responsible people in the city, in addition to the mayor. As the person responsible for these sectors:

Sector 1 - the mayor;

Sector 2 - City Prosecutor;

Head of Urban Affairs for Sector 3;

Sector 4 hides the city's tax chief.

In accordance with the Resolution of the Republican Board of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Republic of Karakalpakstan "Mahalla" Fund No. 136 of May 30, 2014, socio-demographic and economic factors for 2019 were identified and have the following information.

The first sector includes "Guzar", "Darbent", "Bereket", "Railway", "Jeke Terek", "Juazshy", "Jana Bazar", Naukan bag, "Naubakhar", "Silk Road", "Jayhun", " Kyzyl Kum, "Nauryz" and "Bes tobe", a total of 14 citizens' assemblies. The 1st sector area accounts for 32% of the total city of Nukus and is located on the southeastern side of the city. The number of consumers in this sector is 71,916, and the number of households is 14,173. As a result, 21% of the city's total population lives in the area, with 6 people per household. More than 7 km in length from this sector is crossed by the International Railway and the railway station building is located. In the area of this sector the bus station was built for buses and taxis for public transportation, which connects the Amudarya, Turtkul, Ellikala, Beruni districts and all regions of the southern part of Karakalpakstan.

A two-tiered butterfly-like bridge has been built on the highway from all regions of Uzbekistan and on the Great Silk Road to prevent traffic congestion. The area on the south and east sides of Sector 1 has a sandy desert zone of several hundred hectares.

According to demographic factors of the total population in sector 1, the number of young children or under 7 years old is 5753, the total number is 8%. The number of children and adolescents aged 7 to 16 years was 7910, with a total rate of -11%. The number of juveniles and adults or 16 to 30 years of age is 11,146, with a total rate of -15.8%. The rate is 34.8% or 2526 people under the age of 30.

The second sector includes "Kutly makon", "Taslaq", "Yolshylar", "Allaniyaz kaharman", "Kutly konys", "Botanika bagi", "Hao'a yoli", "Aydyn yol", "Sharq", "Doslyq guzary", " Chimboy teahouse ", " Sand aoyl " citizens' gatherings. A total of 12 venues have 28% of the total area of the city of Nukus, located on the south-eastern side of the city. Sector 2 is located on the north side of Nukus. The eastern part of the territory of this sector is bordered by arable lands of Nukus district, while it has several thousand hectares of sand. The number of residents in this sector is 83,431, and the number of farms is 14,399. As a result, 24% of the total city population lives in this area, with 6 people per household. The area is home to an international airport building and grounds. In addition, there is a highway and a bus station building connecting the northern districts with Chimbay, Kegeyli, Takhtakupyr, Karauzyak, Bozatao, Muynak and Nukus districts. Ashshy Lake, which has more than 10 hectares of summer recreation area for tourists from the city and neighboring districts, is home to the Ashar Lake. There are various small architectural objects on the shores of this lake.

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According to demographic factors of the total population in sector 2, the number of young children or children under 7 years of age is 6674, the total number is 8%. The number of children and adolescents aged 7 to 16 years was 8343, with a total rate of -10%. The number of juveniles and juveniles, or 16 to 30 years of age, is 15,018, with a total rate of -18%. The rate is 36% or 3035 people under the age of 30.

The third sector includes "Nur", "Eli abad", "Qurylysshy", "Tynyshlyq", "Shayyrlar", "Sarbinaz", "Gulzar", "Ornek", "Kos Kol", "Doslyq", "Almazar", "Bakhshylyq". ", " Garessizlik ", " Xalqlar dustligi ", "Aq otau ", " Tungish qonis ", a total of 16 venues of public gatherings. The third sector area covers 15% of the city area and is located in the city center. The number of residents is 75,268, while the number of farms is 14,550.

As a result, 22% of the total city population lives in this area, with 5 people per household. The western side of the 3 sectors is bordered by the Doslyk canal, the northern side is bordered by the 2nd sector, the southern and eastern sides are bordered by the 1st sector, and the eastern side is bordered by the North-Western Military District of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main administrative buildings of Nukus, the Central Farmer's Market, the Karakalpak branch of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan and the Savitsky Museum are located in this area.

According to demographic factors of the total population in sector 3, the number of young children or under 7 years old is 6021, the total number is 8%. The number of children and adolescents from 7 to 16 years is 7527, the total number is -10%. The number of juveniles and juveniles or 16 to 30 years of age is 9935, with a total rate of 13.2%. The proportion under the age of 30 is 31.2% or a total of 23,483 people.

The fourth sector includes "Tele Oray", "Boz Aoyl", "Anasay", "Samanbay", "Jiydeli-Baysyn", "Amudarya", "Qos Bulaq", "Bayterek", "Naupir", "Kattag'ar", "Gone Sheher". ", " Turan ", " Kok ozek ", " Qumbyz aoyl ", " Aq jagys " a total of 15 venues are located in the western part of Nukus. The territory of the fourth sector occupies 25% of the area of the city, with a population of 103,157 and a household of 16,278, with 6 people per household. The western side of the fourth sector is bordered by the Amudarya River, and the eastern side by the Doslyk Canal. This sector completely covers the area of Nukus called "Gone kala" (old city). A mosque with a high level of modern architectural solutions in the city of Nukus, a bus station connecting the western districts with Kungrad, Shumanay, Lake Kanly, Khojeli. In the western districts there is a 1 km long bridge crossing the Amudarya River on the highway. The bridge was built in 1993 and is planned to cross the bridge on the newly built Great Silk Road.

According to demographic factors of the total population in sector 4, the number of young children or children under 7 years of age - 7633 total - 7.4%. Children and adolescents from 7 to 16 years of age - 11347, the total number - 11%. The number of juveniles and juveniles or 16 to 30 years of age is 16,505, with a total rate of 16%. The proportion under 30 is 34.4% or a total of 35,485.

As a result, the city has a population of 350,000 and 59 places are divided into citizens' assemblies. In Nukus, each venue has an average population of 6,000. According to the demographic factors of the total population of the city, the total number of young children or children under 7 years - 26081 - 7.5%. Children and adolescents from 7 to 16 years of age - 35,127, the total number - 10%. The number of juveniles and juveniles or 16 to 30 years of age is 52,604, with a total rate of -15%. This means that the proportion of the population under the age of 30 in the city is 32.5% or a total of 113,812.

III. CONCLUSION.

The choice of the village of Nukus as the capital, the convenience for development, the positive design of the architectural masterpiece, taking into account the future, formed a demographic data on the population growth 35 times over 90 years. Illegal housing construction was found to be the reason for the architectural inconsistency in the suburbs of the city. To address these shortcomings, there should be an additional staff of architects as the Deputy Chief Architect of the City. The reason is that Nukus has less control over a single architect. Taking into account the development of the city, demographic growth, at least 20 years of perspective project proposals must be approved and approved by the leaders of each community, and strict control over their territory. The following proposals need to be implemented in order for the city to become a megalopolis soon.

1. Given the shortcomings in the city of Nukus, if each city and district has 4 sectors, one architect should be assigned to each state as the chief architect of this sector.
2. Illegal land use is on the rise in cities and counties. Each sector architect carries out public awareness work. If it does not accept the warning, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan in its Resolution No. 41 of 12 February 2009 will take additional measures to strengthen control over the strict implementation of urban planning norms and rules in the complex construction of settlements and by this, the salary of the architecture can be covered.
3. It is necessary to form a small and a large ring road in Nukus to prevent congestion on highways in the future.

Figure.1. Nukus city general history map and 4 sector areas.

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